

Review

Without parvovirus B19 infection of thyroid tissues, no Hashimoto's thyroiditis

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Aim: Whether a Parvovirus B19 viral infection is responsible for Hashimoto's thyroiditis remains unclear. Studies addressing this issue were re-analyzed.

Materials and methods: The electronic database PubMed has been searched for appropriate studies. New statistical methods were applied to gain some new knowledge. The p Values less than .05 were considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

Results: The data re-analyzed support the null-hypothesis: without parvovirus B19 infection of human thyroid tissues no Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Furthermore, the considered for re-analysis support the null-hypothesis of a sufficient and of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship between parvovirus B19 infection of human thyroid tissues no Hashimoto's thyroiditis. The causal relationship between a parvovirus B19 infection of human thyroid tissues no Hashimoto's thyroiditis is statistically highly significant. The conclusion is inescapable.

Conclusions: Without parvovirus B19 infection of human thyroid tissues no Hashimoto's thyroiditis.

INTRODUCTION

Hashimoto's thyroiditis (HT), named after Japanese physician Hakaru Hashimoto^{1,2} (1881–1934) of the medical school at Kyushu University, is a very common disorder of the human thyroid gland in which the thyroid gland is gradually destroyed. Under usual circumstances, HT is typically treated with levothyroxine. Etiologically, HT has been linked to a combination of genetic and environmental³ factors including infections with Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), human T-lymphotropic virus-1 (HTLV-1), hepatitis C, *Yersinia enterocolitica* and Parvovirus B19 (B19). The global prevalence of human parvovirus B19, discovered 1974 by Cossart et al.⁴, is high. Nevertheless, theoretically it is to be assumed that B19 is causally related with HT. However, studies published provided insufficient evidence for the viral hypothesis in Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Therefore, the potential role of B19 infection in inducing Hashimoto's thyroiditis is re-investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Literature search

In October 2021, the electronic databases PubMed was searched for all (or most) potentially relevant articles. The following keywords were used in combination: “Parvovirus B19 and Hashimoto”. In order to increase the transparency of the research process and the reliability of published knowledge, reporting follows in adherence to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis^{5,6}.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies in English language which investigated the relationship between B19 and HT were considered. Studies with data access barriers were not considered. Reviews, case reports, letters, conference abstracts, or expert opinions were excluded and not considered.

Study selection and characteristics

The literature search yielded 18 potentially eligible titles. The abstracts were reviewed, inappropriate articles were excluded and removed. At the end, 3 articles⁷⁻⁹ (**Table 1**) which met the inclusion criteria and were eligible for meta-analyses.

Table 1. The PRISMA literature screening flow chart.

Identification:	Pubmed	18
Screening:	Articles excluded I	8
Eligibility:	Articles eligible for analysis	10
	Articles excluded II (language, data access et cetera)	7
Inclusion:	Studies included (meta-analysis)	3

Wang et al.¹⁰ provided very convincing data about the relationship between the expression of PR domain zinc finger protein 1 (PRDM1) and HT (**Table 2**). However, it was not possible to access the data on the relationship between PRDM1 and B19. Therefore, the study has not been considered.

Table 2. PRDM1 and HT.

		Hashimoto thyroiditis		Total
		Yes	No	
PRDM1	Yes	83	0	83
	No	3	30	33
Total		86	30	116

Nasikas et al.¹¹ provided self-contradictory data (exclusion relationship significant and condition sine qua non relationship significant, which is logically not possible). The data of Nasikas et al. have not been considered for re-analysis.

Data extraction and assessment of study quality

The data from articles which met which the inclusion and exclusion criteria were extracted and statistically analyzed. The data and the statistical analyses of the three studies are presented in detail (**Table 3-5**). The statistical analyses of the study of Hartwig W. Lehmann et al.⁷ is presented by **table 4**. The study design has been very unfair ($p(\text{IOU})=0,425$).

Table 3. The study of Hartwig W. Lehmann et al.⁷.

		Hashimoto thyroiditis		Total
		Yes	No	
B19 DNA	Yes	9	2	11
	No	64	71	135
Total		73	73	146

Table 4. Statistical analysis of the study of Hartwig W. Lehmann et al.⁷.

Statistical analysis	
Causal relationship k =	+0,18165
P Value right tailed (HGD) =	0,0277900
p (IMP) =	0,986
X ² (IMP A _t) =	0,364
X ² (IMP B _t) =	0,055
p(IOU) =	0,425

The data and the statistical analyses of the study of Juanhong Wang et al.⁸ are presented by two tables (**Table 5 and Table 6**). However, the study design of the study of Wang et al.⁸ has been very unfair ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,417$).

Table 5. The study of Juanhong Wang et al.⁸.

		Hashimoto thyroiditis		Total
		Yes	No	
B19 DNA	Yes	29	7	36
	No	3	9	12
Total		32	16	48

Table 6. Statistical analysis of the study of Juanhong Wang et al.⁸.

Statistical analysis	
Causal relationship $k = +0,51031$	
p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,0008735	
p (SINE) = 0,937500	
$X^2(\text{SINE} \underline{B}_t) = 0,281$	
$X^2(\text{SINE} \underline{A}_t) = 0,750$	
p (IMP) = 0,854	
$X^2(\text{IMP} \underline{A}_t) = 1,361$	
$X^2(\text{IMP} \underline{B}_t) = 3,063$	
p (SINE ^ IMP) = 0,792	
$X^2(\text{SINE}^{\wedge}\text{IMP} \underline{A}_t) = 2,111$	
$X^2(\text{SINE}^{\wedge}\text{IMP} \underline{B}_t) = 3,344$	
$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,417$	

Adamson et al.⁹ detected B19 capsid protein by immunohistochemistry (IHC) in various types of thyroid disorders. “Twenty-one of the 24 (88%) PTC tumors ... and 3 of the 3 HT tissue samples were positive for B19 capsid protein by immunohistochemistry.”⁹ This data are presented by **table 7**.

Table 7. The study of Adamson et al.⁹.

		Hashimoto thyroiditis		Total
		Yes	No	
B19 capsid protein (IHC)	Yes	3	21	24
	No	0	3	3
Total		3	24	24

The statistical analysis of the study of Adamson et al.⁹ is presented by **table 8**.

Table 8. Statistical analysis of the study of Adamson et al.⁹.

Statistical analysis
Causal relationship $k = +0,12500$
P Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,6919658
p (SINE) = 1,000000
$X^2(\text{SINE} B_t) = 0,000$
$X^2(\text{SINE} A_t) = 0,000$
$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,000$

Statistical methods

The necessary¹² condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has tested for statistical significance. The sufficient¹² condition relationship $p(\text{IMP})$ has been calculated and has been proofed for statistical significance too. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit a certain theoretical distribution in the population. The causal¹² relationship k has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events/factors analyzed. The hyper-geometric¹³⁻¹⁵ distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship k . The study (design) bias has been controlled by IOI, the index of independence¹⁶ and IOU, the index of unfairness¹⁷. All the data were analyzed using MS EXCEL (Microsoft Corporation, USA). The p values¹⁸ less than .05 were considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

RESULTS

The data presented provided evidence of a necessary condition relationship (p(SINE)) between B19 infection of thyroid tissues and Hashimoto's thyroiditis. In other words, *without* parvovirus B19 infection of thyroid tissues, *no* Hashimoto's thyroiditis (**Table 6, Table 8**). The study of Lehmann et al.⁷ (**Table 4**) and the study of Wang et al.⁸ (**Table 6**) documented evidence of a statistically significant sufficient condition relationship (p(IMP)) between B19 infection and Hashimoto's thyroiditis. In other words, *if* parvovirus B19 infection of thyroid tissues, *then* Hashimoto's thyroiditis (**Table 6, Table 8**). Wang et al.⁸ provided additional evidence (**Table 6**) of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship between B19 infection of thyroid tissues and Hashimoto's thyroiditis while the causal relationship k is greater than zero and statistically highly significant ($k=+0,51031$; p Value = $0,0008735$). From that point of view and in the overall view of the data analyzed it appears appropriate and justified to conclude that B19 infection of thyroid tissues is the cause of Hashimoto's thyroiditis ($k=+0,51031$; p Value = $0,0008735$).

DISCUSSION

Investigations conducted under identical condition which differ only in terms of study design or sample size may point the researcher in different directions. A sample should not be small but not excessive too. When re-analyzing the data of a study one of the main implications is the sample size but, contrary to what one might think, the design of a study too. An inappropriate study design is a formal and strategic disadvantage which has taken place making it near enough impossible to recognize the true state of affairs. Bearing this point in mind, an erroneous study design can compromise the conclusions drawn from the studies. And it gets worse: the study design of the majority of the studies analyzed in this publication has been very unfair. Of course, under such circumstances, at least at first sight, one can choose the easy way by demanding that it does not make at all any sense to come to one conclusion. However, one simply has to realize that the studies analyzed do not agree completely at every point, but the same studies does not contradict themselves too. We are not completely unaffected by the fact that more investigations will be required and are necessary to gain a better insight into the relationship between B19 and HT. In spite of all this, and against all the setbacks, the following preliminary conclusions are justified.

CONCLUSION

Without parvovirus B19 infection of thyroid tissues, *no* Hashimoto's thyroiditis (**Table 6, Table 6**). And much more than this. A parvovirus B19 infection of thyroid tissues is the cause of Hashimoto's thyroiditis (**Table 6**).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author has no conflicts of interest to declare.

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